

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY
BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 1st meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held in Dean's chamber of College of Physiotherapy, City campus, Pandeshwar on **15.05.2017**.

Members present were:

- Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *S. Rajasekar*
Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*
Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala*
Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*
Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) *Prameela*
Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) *Padmakumar*

Members not present were:

- Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovala (External Member) **ABSENT**

At the onset the Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar welcomed the members and placed the agenda for the deliberations of the members. The following deliberations were made as per the circulated agenda:

- 1. To consider and approve the Curriculum and syllabus for BPT and MPT.**
 - The Chairperson informed the house that the curriculum and syllabus for BPT and MPT for the batch of 2017 was structured and ready for approval.
 - Resolution:** The members considered the curriculum and syllabus for BPT and MPT and discussed different issues. Finally, it was approved and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval. It was also decided that the course can be introduced under College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University from 2017 onwards.

- 2. Planning the academic calendar for BPT and MPT for the academic year 2017-18.**
 - Chairperson, Dr. S. Rajasekar requested that the academic calendar for the odd semesters of BPT and MPT be planned for the year 2017-18 (June- December 2018).
 - Resolution:** The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2017-18 of odd semesters of BPT and MPT and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

3. Formation of Board of Examiners (BOE) for BPT and MPT programmes for 2017-18.

The Chairperson explained the criteria related to the selection of BOE members and requested the Board to suggest names.

-Resolution: The Board prepared the list of BOE members in the Physiotherapy programmes for the academic year 2017-18 and resolved to recommend the same to the University.

4. Introduction of Value added courses for BPT and MPT for the year 2017-18.

Chairperson explained the requirement for adding value added course (not a part of curriculum) for BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The board discussed on this matter and it was decided that,

- for BPT 1st year- Basic Nursing and First Aid
- for MPT 1st year- Basic Life Support

These courses will be of minimum 30 hours and will be applicable for the batches of 2017.

The meeting started at 10.00am and ended at 12.30pm with Thanks to the Chair.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY
BOS MINUTES OF THE MEETING

The 2nd meeting of BOS of College of Physiotherapy, Srinivas University was held at Srinivas College of Physiotherapy, Pandeshwar on 09.10.2017

Members present were:

Dr. S. Rajasekar (Chairperson) *SR*

Dr. Ajay Kumar (Member) *Ajay*

Dr. Thrishala Noronha (Member) *Thrishala*

Dr. Annayya Kulal Ulthoor (Member) *Annayya*

Dr. Prameela P. Hubli (Member) *Prameela*

Members not present were:

Dr. Padmakumar (External Member) ABSENT

Dr. Rakesh Krishna Kovala (External Member) ABSENT

The Chairperson welcomed the members present followed by discussion and resolution of agenda items:

- 1. Confirmation of minutes of last meeting of the Board of Studies held on 15.05.2017.**
- The minutes of the BOS meeting held on 15th May 2017 were circulated among the BOS members. Since no comment has been received, this BOS has approved the minutes of the BOS meeting.

- 2. Planning the academic calendar for II semester of BPT for the period from December 2017 to April 2018.**
-The Chairperson requested that the academic calendar for the II semester of BPT be planned for the year 2017-18 (December 2017-April 2018).
-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2017-18 of II semester of BPT and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

- 3. Planning the academic calendar for II semester of MPT for the period of March 2018 to August 2018.**

-The Chairperson requested that the academic calendar for the II semester of MPT be planned for the year 2017-18 (March-August 2018).

-Resolution: The members discussed and structured the academic calendar for the academic year 2017-18 of II semester of MPT and recommended to the Academic Council for further approval.

4. Preparation of Panel of examiners/gradation list.

The Chairperson requested the Board members to prepare the panel of examiners for the 1st and 2nd semester end examination of BPT and MPT programmes.

-Resolution: The Board members prepared the panel of examiners for the 1st and 2nd semester end examination of BPT and MPT programmes and resolved to recommend the same to the University and send the panel of examiners list in a sealed cover to Registrar (Evaluation).

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and co-operation.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Chairperson
BOS, College of Physiotherapy

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